

GAME MANUAL

Congratulations, your research project was accepted!

Now it is time to publish your results and findings. What may happen along the way and what you have to be aware of will be presented in this game. Nevertheless, you are not alone – your library will be there every step of the way. Dive into the world of scientific publishing and gather a high reputation in your community through smart decisions.

GOAL OF THE GAME

As a scientist, you seek impact and visibility by building a well-established reputation.

GAME INFORMATION

- Every player starts with 5 coins.
- Every player starts with 0 reputation tokens.

HOW TO PLAY

Roll and movement

Roll the dice in turns and move the corresponding number of spaces.

- When you enter a library or open access space, complete the action.
- When you enter an action field, read the action card aloud and follow the instructions.
Action can provide assistance or pose a challenge.

Fees and scientific publishing

Unfortunately, academic publishing is not always free of charge. Be careful how you spend your coins and earn reputation tokens through libraries and open access principles.

Spaces and action fields

When you enter a library or open access field or draw an action card causing costs, you must pay with your game coins. The game master will tell you the costs, or they are written on the action card.

Out of coins

If you cannot pay any coins, you will be asked to give up reputation tokens (vice versa).
If you have neither coins nor reputation tokens, you pause one turn.

END OF THE GAME

**The game is finished when one player gains 5 or more reputation tokens.
This player has the highest scientific impact and visibility and is the winner of the game!**